

Deep Learning for the Detection of Frames of Interest in Fetal Heart Assessment from First Trimester Ultrasound

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Abstract. The current paper challenges convolutional neural networks to address the computationally undebated task of recognizing four key views in first trimester fetal heart scanning (the aorta, the arches, the atrioventricular flows and the crossing of the great vessels). This is the primary inspection of the heart of a future baby and an early recognition of possible problems is important for timely intervention. Frames depicting the views of interest were labeled by obstetricians and given to several deep learning architectures as a classification task against other irrelevant scan sights. A test accuracy of 95% with an F1-score ranging from 90.91% to 99.58% for the four key perspectives shows the potential in supporting heart scans even from such an early fetal age, when the heart is still quite underdeveloped.

Keywords: deep learning, classification, fetal heart, ultrasound, first trimester pregnancy

1 Introduction

Medicine is one of the main and most important stages where deep learning (DL) has been playing a successful role during the last couple of years [6, 16, 20]. Its models have targeted the recognition of a wide range of diseases on the base of various image types, from histopathological slides [1, 14, 18, 24] to MRI scans [17, 22, 29] and CT [4, 15], to name several recent entries in the medical areas mostly used for computer vision.

A further challenging scope has become to use DL models for a more complex task, i.e. to analyze medical data coming from video scans [28]. A good choice

for such a problem is fetal ultrasound (US), where there is a moving patient-in-patient. An even more stimulating scenario is to additionally examine an organ in motion, e.g. the heart.

Medically speaking, fetal echocardiography (FECG) is one of the crucial US assessments during pregnancy towards an early detection of possible congenital heart disease (CHD) [13]. The disease accounts for 50% of childhood deaths attributed to congenital malformations [19, 21]. The US assessment can allow immediate intervention after birth, or even intrauterine treatment, and an associated decreased cost of care. While screening for CHD started with the high-risk groups (genetic, environmental factors), it is now generally advocated, due to many cases discovered in low-risk pregnancies [3]. For the first trimester, however, the guidelines do not impose the obligation of screening for CHD as the heart structures are underdeveloped. Nevertheless, an early detection of the condition is desirable to start with the first trimester [9, 10], when the pregnancy can be terminated in case of severe abnormalities, or that can be correlated with the findings of the subsequent trimester [11].

In a FECG, the physicians look for the absence, distortion or improper positioning of different heart components per se or in relation to one another, as well as for an incorrect blood flow in the heart. The difficulty in the analysis of the fetal heart generally stems from several acknowledged facets [2, 7]: the low expertise in fetal echocardiography of early stage sonographers, the absence of a standardized protocol, the susceptibility of US imaging to noise given by the presence of shadows, the ambiguity of the structures due to the small heart size, the variability of the disposal of the heart and its components due to the movement of the probe, the activity of the fetus and the fetus-probe orientation, as well as the existence of different viewing planes (apical, lateral).

In this context, DL models can serve as a virtual assistant and indicate to the clinician the views of interest with the presence or the absence of certain characteristics of importance in the CHD diagnosis. Among the existing literature entries, described in more detail in Section 2, all of which dealing with computational heart assessment from second trimester scans, the current paper differently and firstly considers a DL architecture to recognize the elementary structures and behavior that are present in a first trimester FECG, especially given the absence of compulsory screening invoked by the low development of the heart. Several distinct elements were highlighted by studies regarding the heart anatomy in the first trimester that should be visible in the color Doppler US scans or the lack of any of them already implies a possible anomaly that needs to be further investigated by the sonographer. To our knowledge, this is the first study concerning computational support for heart screening during the first trimester (12-14 weeks gestational age).

The paper is structured as follows. A review of the works dealing with second trimester fetal heart inspection from the US are depicted in Section 2. The data set is then described in Section 3. The employed methodology for the recognition of crucial frames is explained in Section 4, also addressing the prior data pre-

processing step. The experiments are outlined in Section 5, and the conclusions and prospective directions are given in Section 6.

2 State of the Art in Fetal Heart Assessment

Computational support for the complex problem of fetal cardiac video analysis has appeared solely in the last couple of years and it is scarce, as compared to those works approaching echo- and electrocardiography. Moreover, the state of the art in automated analysis of the fetal heart has targeted only the second trimester examination for CHD detection, as shown below.

The study [2] took 91 US videos from 12 subjects (with a gestational age of 20 to 35 weeks) and appointed a combination of a particle-filtering method, for connecting the predictions from multiple frames, and a random forest predictor, to estimate cardiac phase, viewing plane, visibility, position and orientation from each one. However, CHD cannot be identified and the results are not integrated into the video scan. The work progresses in [8], where a three-task learning model is formulated towards heart view classification, localization and orientation. Three heart views of second trimester scans are detected against background through classification with a VGGNet. Detection is conducted through a circular anchor mechanism. Localization is achieved through an intersection over union loss, while orientation through a cosine one. A bi-directional LSTM is employed to add the temporal information over frames.

In [5], 615 cardiac US frames of fetuses with a normal heart condition at 18–28 weeks were collected, in almost 50%-50% apical/non-apical orientation. The task set was to accurately segment the ventricular septum. This was performed using a combination of YOLO, U-Net and VGG-16, while also referring to pre- and post-cropped frames through an encoder-decoder component in order to take time into account.

The paper [12] has assigned a Yolov2 object detection model to localize and classify 18 heart components from US scans of 363 subjects, taken at 18-34 weeks. The bounding box detected for each structure and the probability associated is displayed in real time. Additionally a binary colored barcode corresponding to the detection of each heart element is represented along the scanning timeline. The approach is however based on the assumption that the fetus scan is always performed in a fixed direction from the stomach, through the heart, to the vascular arches (taken mostly in the apical view); thus the heart appears in the same position in all the US frames. Training was performed on the normal cases only, and the 14 CHD cases were used for test, where an abnormality score computed the total number of well detected components.

In contrast, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to perform first trimester heart analysis at 12-14 weeks old gestational age from fetal echocardiography. Heart examination in the first trimester is yet more difficult, given the even lower structural development of the organ components present at this early stage. The paper therefore aims to distinguish the key frames that must be present in the heart sweep by formulating the problem into a classification

task and solving it through DL architectures. Afterwards, the selected and classified frames will be analyzed by the physician. Additionally, if not all four key views are detected, then the physician is alerted to look more attentively for the missing components.

3 Data set

The current work aims to detect the presence/absence of key frames from first trimester US videos. Given that some component cannot be viewed is already an early indicator of a heart condition. The four key frames to be distinguished are represented by the main planes of the cardiac sweep with color Doppler applied [27]: the atrioventricular (AV) flows in four-chamber view plane (hereinafter, AV flows), the aorta in the left ventricular outflow tract plane (hereinafter, aorta), the crossing of the great vessels (the X sign) in the right ventricular outflow tract plane and the arches (the V sign) in three-vessel plane.

These views that must be learnt and further discovered in a new video were provided by the physicians in meaningful images extracted from US scans. They are taken only in the apical plane. The US videos were recorded by distinct machines, namely General Electric Voluson E10, E8 and E6 systems, GE Healthcare, Zipf, Austria, equipped with RAB 4-8-D (2-8 MHz), RAB 6D (2-7 MHz), and RM6C (2-6 MHz) transducers. Also, sonographers with different degrees of expertise have conducted the examinations. These prerequisites were taken in order to allow for variability in the rendering performance of the machine and the human experience and thus test the generalization ability of the model.

The data set consists of 326 US scans of fetuses age 12-14 weeks. There are some patients that have several examinations recorded. The collection was split into training/validation/test subsets, making sure that the videos of a same patient are not present at the intersection of any two subsets. All the data have been preprocessed, following the procedure outlined in subsection 4.1. Figure 1 shows that the features that ought to be present vary greatly from one scan to another, due to the conditions already stated before in the introduction, the color or directional power Doppler approach, and the software and ultrasound machine type.

4 Methodology

DL is applied to the given frames only after a preceding preprocessing, in order to set the focus on the cardiac area of the fetus and ignore the background area.

4.1 Data preprocessing

In order to achieve this goal, first the area of interest is marked with a red circle. Recognizing it is however not straightforward, as it has an irregular shape and positioning, a similar color to the neighbouring tissues and is not easily separable

Fig. 1. Examples of different frames showing the four key appearances that ought to be present in the first trimester fetal heart (each on one row). From top to bottom: the aorta, the V sign, the AV flows, and the X sign.

from the surrounding areas. Nevertheless, it always covers the center of the image and it is connected with the other tissues through narrow bridges.

Further, since most of the frames are dual, showing both the standard gray-scale mapping US capture, on the left, and the Doppler interrogation, on the right, the subsequent phase is to separate the two sides of an image. Then, a procedure in six steps was used. Firstly, the image is converted to gray scale and a threshold is applied to eliminate background noise. Then, erosion with a 10x10 pixels kernel is performed in order to eliminate the connecting bridges. Thirdly, the spots that cover the central area of the image are identified and the spot with the highest coverage is taken. Next, dilation with the same 10x10 pixels kernel is applied in order to restore the dimension of the selected spot. Subsequently, the convex hull of the dilated spot is drawn and filled. Finally, the generated spot is used as the mask to extract the area of interest.

4.2 Frame Classification

The preprocessed frames are next investigated for the detection of the four key views of the first trimester fetal heart.

Their identification can be further transposed into a classification problem with five categories: the four compulsorily present structures (aorta, V sign, AV flows and X sign) and further unimportant shapes that can be seen in the video (referred next as "other").

Hence a CNN architecture is appointed to independently learn the features indicative of each view and perform the classification. Once it is able to recognize each view, the final aim becomes that, when presented with a new video, the model takes it frame by frame and signals those views that it found as present in the scan.

Fig. 2. Illustration of the number of sample US images per each training-validation-test set, as well as per class.

5 Experiments

Several models were chosen and the findings support the use of DL for this task.

5.1 Setup

Six DL architectures were fine tuned on the training frames: DenseNet-201, Inception-V4, ResNet-152, ResNet-18, ResNet-50 and Xception. The metric that is targeted by the models is the classification accuracy.

As mentioned in subsection 4.1, the input images contain only a cropped section of the US scans, i.e. the one from the right side, where the color Doppler is present. These images were resized to 224×224 pixels. The options used for data augmentation contain a random image flip with a probability of 0.5, a probability of 0.75 for a random rotation between -10 and 10 degrees, a random zoom of up to 1.1 times the image, a random lightning and contrast change controlled by a threshold of 0.2 and a random symmetric warp of magnitude between -0.2 and 0.2. There are images from 192 US scans in the training set, from another 67 in the validation one and finally from the remaining 67 in the test set. In each separate set, there may be several US scans from the same person, but taken at different times. However, there is no patient that appears at the intersection of any two subsets. The total number of images in all sets and all classes is 7251. From these, 4260 are in the training set, 1495 in validation and 1496 in the test set. The split per class is shown in Figure 2.

A 1cycle policy [23] is used for the training process, at first with 10 epochs and afterwards unfreezing all layers and training for another 10 epochs. The learning rate is fine-tuned for each architecture in turn and its values are chosen according to the strategy proposed in [23]. The batch size was taken equal to 32. The experiments are made on Google Colab, using a Tesla T4 GPU. The source codes are written in Python with the Pytorch and Fast.ai libraries.

Accuracy (%)	DenseNet201	InceptionV4	ResNet152	ResNet18	ResNet50	Xception
Validation	97.34	97.23	96.65	97.27	97.23	96.72
Test	95.56	94.38	94.42	95.34	95.52	94.96

Table 1. Mean validation and test accuracy obtained by the 6 models.

Measures (%)	Aorta	V Sign	AV Flows	X Sign	Other	Macro average	Weighted avg
Precision	92.86	96.69	99.58	91.4	98.35	95.77	97.21
Recall	94.55	98.87	99.58	90.43	97.28	96.14	97.19
F1-score	93.69	97.77	99.58	90.91	97.81	95.95	97.19

Table 2. Precision, recall and F1-score in a test run with confusion matrix in Fig. 3

5.2 Results

The validation and test accuracy, reported in mean after 5 repeated runs, are shown in Table 1. The confusion matrix reached in one run is depicted in Figure 3. Its accompanying metrics are outlined in Table 2.

Figure 4 shows that, if we put a confidence threshold for the largest output of the last Softmax layer, the number of mislabeled samples decreases, with some loss in accuracy. The example is run on the same run whose output is presented in Figure 3 and Table 2. The results are discussed in the next subsection.

Fig. 3. The confusion matrix obtained on the test samples in the most accurate run of DenseNet201. The accuracy is 97.19%. The other related metrics are given in Table 2.

5.3 Discussion

The fastest architecture from the tried ones is, as expected, ResNet-18, which needs in average 12 minutes for 10 epochs of fitting the 1cycle policy. Note however that the model is twice trained for 10 epochs, at first using a large set of layers frozen and then after unfreezing them. Additionally, after unfreezing, there is also a process of searching for an appropriate learning rate that takes slightly more than 5 minutes for ResNet-18. The entire process of loading the data, training, validation and then applying the model on the test set lasts for the same model almost 35 minutes. The running times for training 10 epochs using 1cycle policy take for ResNet-50 13.2 minutes, 15.5 for Xception, 23.6 for InceptionV4, and 26.2 for ResNet152 and DenseNet201.

The five models analyzed have achieved significantly high accuracy results; all in a narrow margin. These results confirm the viability of our CNN proposal to work with data from the first trimester of pregnancy. The best result obtained in a single run on the test set is achieved by the DenseNet201 architecture and it is detailed in Figure 3 and Table 2. A small number of frames belonging to

Fig. 4. The confidence threshold reduced the number of samples that are mistaken at the cost of decreasing the accuracy. Accuracy+Other reconsiders the accuracy after assigning all samples with probability below the threshold to *Other*. First row shows the results on the validation set, while the second refers to the test set.

the *Other* class are mistaken for key views, especially the Aorta and the X sign. These two elements are described by a smaller number of frames in the data set (see Figure 2).

The inclusion of a large amount of samples from *Other* class is intended to reflect the large amount of samples in a US video that should not be labeled as one of the important 4 classes. This class covers a relatively large and random type of arrangement of the components (flows in different shapes and colors, while in some frames they can even be absent). A part of them are also relatively close to the views that correspond to key structures like Aorta or X sign, hence there are cases that may mislead the model.

In an attempt to further make use of the outputs of the last Softmax layer, we experiment a shallow approach of using a confidence threshold in the following manner: assign a validation or test sample to a class only if the largest output from the Softmax corresponds to that certain class and its value is larger than the threshold. In the left plots in Figure 4 we represent the accuracy when the model simply ignores the samples whose values are below the threshold. A first decision is to not assign them to any class, but simply consider them as mislabelled in the computation of the metric and forward them to the obstetrician for assessment. The second option (*Accuracy + Other*) attributes the class *Other* to these samples. Naturally, the latter leads to a better classification accuracy and actually represents a viable scenario, since the expert is in fact especially interested in the first 4 classes, and not in the *Other* samples. However, there are still some samples that are mislabeled and their values from the Softmax remain

larger than the threshold, and these are illustrated in the plots from the right side. The trend is very similar for both the validation (first row) and the test (second row) cases. For instance, when we set a threshold of 0.99, an accuracy of 84.28% is achieved on the validation set by putting away the samples with the Softmax output below the threshold, while, if they are assigned to *Other*, the accuracy increases to 91.51%. The corresponding values for the test set when putting the same threshold are of 83.42% and 88.1%, respectively. The percentage of the remaining errors in the setting of this threshold is 0% for validation and 0.53% for the test set (i.e. samples with Softmax outputs greater than the threshold, but mislabelled).

6 Conclusions

The current research consists of constructing a CNN model able to accurately identify and classify several key frames from a first trimester fetal heart scanning. To do this, as a preliminary step, we have built a classification data set of US frames denoting the fetal heart from this pregnancy period. This can aid the physician to further take a decision regarding the presumption of a normal condition (when all the key frames are present) or the acquisition of further scans when they are absent, since there could be a problematic situation.

There are six CNN architectures tried and fine-tuned for the given task and the results on the test set are of around 95.5% for correctly classifying 1496 samples. They are very encouraging, since even if an error that is below 5% is present, a US video recording of up to 5 seconds of a healthy fetal heart usually contains more than one key frame for each class in turn, and therefore it is very likely that at least one frame per class is detected.

We also propose a shallow approach to test the confidence of the results. While this comes at a cost of losing some samples from reaching a weaker decision on them, the error rate is decreased both on the validation and on the test sets. Although this experiment shows promising results, we intend to deal with uncertainty [25, 26] in future work to model more objective thresholds.

The data set will continue to be expanded and we expect to reach an even better overall accuracy. Also we intend to adjust the loss in such a way as to disadvantage the mislabeling of the *Other* samples as significant key frames. Another task that is intended for future work is to be able to further indicate normal/abnormal condition in key frames detected as present.

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